

Paper 14**EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM INITIATES
TO MANAGE THE PERFORMANCE OF THE
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Abstract:

In the recent days because of globalization there is a rapid change in the developmental concepts of the industry. Industries want to establish new sophisticated Employee development technologies to improve the quality and to produce the standards products in the market. Improving and giving modernized Employee development touch to the machines are not only important concept in the corporate world. But more than that majority of the companies want to develop their employees to achieve the desired Employee development result. Employees are the real asset for the company; it is the duty of the every HR department has to make a good plan for employee development. HR department has to execute many employee development projects based Employee development on the employee developments of the employees in the organization. Proper research oriented Employee development activities will help the companies to find out the areas where employees are require Employee development to develop their skill. Development of employees is ongoing process in the every company by looking at the future prospective. Development will increase the ability, skill and competitive positions of the employees. This will lead to increase the productivity of the employees and increase the production ability of the company. Employee development projects are the investment on employees for the future to get good returns from them. Developing a good work team will always turns as a real asset for the company. This paper designed Employee development with a purpose that to identify the areas where employees are want to be develop themselves and take necessary step to meet the requirements of the employees. Research tools are developed Employee development to analyze the data collected Employee development to interpret the result in the meaningful way. Theoretical part is developed on the basis of statistical analysis to know the importance of the employee development.

Key words: corporate, projects, skill and ability.

1. Introduction

Employee is a key element of the organization. The success or failure of the organization depends on employee performance. Therefore, organizations are investing huge amount of money on employee development programmes. Implementation of employee development programme and managing employee performance every day is the key to an effective

performance management system. Setting goals, making sure your expectations are clear, and providing frequent Employee development feedback help people perform most effectively. Managing the performance of the employee with the help of employee development programmes plays a very vital role in each and every organisation. The objectives of the organisations will be more effective when employees actively participate in employee developmental programmes and gives good performance to achieve organisational objectives. For this both employee and employer plays important role. There is direct relationship between employee performance and organizational effectiveness. Managing performance of employee with Employee development programmes is not just the responsibility of the employee. In today's diverse workforce, business practices have evolved Employee development to reflect economic competitiveness in developing and retaining talented Employee development employees. Organizations are continually seeking new solutions to assess, understand, and strategize employee development. One of the greatest challenges faced Employee development by managers is the strategic personal development of their employees in order to ensure effective use of their talent. To properly manage this vital resource, they must identify their challenges and then implement employee development and training for improvement.

2. Objectives of the study

1. To know the importance of employee development programmes in an organisation.
2. To establish relationship between performance of the organisation with employee development programme.
3. To find the role of employee and employer or manager on managing performance of the organization.
4. To identify is there any affect of employee development to employee performance.
5. To know the importance of employee development programme to achieve organisational objectives.

3. Employee development for the present study

1. To suggest organizations that overall goals of the organisations can be achieved Employee development when there is active participation by employee and employer.
2. To remove the perception as employee development as a cost in financial terms rather than an investment in the assets of organisation.
3. Recommending that performance of employee can be increased Employee development by providing effective employee development programme.
4. To ensure that employee development is essential to the employees within the organisation.
5. To ensure that environmental changes will require employee development programmes.

4. Methodology applied

The research is developed through primary and secondary source of data. Primary data obtained through issue of questionnaires. The sample size taken for this research is 50 respondents randomly selected from Mangalore and Puttur taluk of Dakshina Kannada district. Theoretical information collected through referring secondary source such as books, journals and magazines.

5. Principal goals of performance management through employee development programme.

1. Improve employee performance:

Employers expect good performance by employees to attain a goal of organisation. Most employers adopt performance management processes primarily to help employees perform more effectively in their current positions and to be more successful in accomplishing organizational goals and also provides different training and developmental programmes to achieve organizational goals.

2. Develop people for promotional opportunities:

When the organisation provides good developmental programmes and manage the performance of the organisation properly this will provide more promotional opportunities to the employee. By providing training and developmental programmes to the employees it will help to develop people for the future new assignments. Employee developmental programmes can serve to help develop people for new assignments and promotional opportunities.

3. Meet Employees' employee development for feedback:

Majority of the employees want to know how they are doing on the job. When there is proper management of performance of the employee by providing employee development programmes this will help the employees to know about their performance standard and they would like to get positive feedback from their employer about their accomplishments and suggestions on how they can improve.

4. Ensure that employees are working toward organisational goals;

This is another important principal goal of managing performance through employee development. When the employer provide employee development programme to employees, obviously employer expect some efforts from employee to achieve organisational goals.

6. Role of Employee Development in the present scenario

The development of people is essential. Employee development is not just training. It has a much broader range of components that have a deeper impact on an individual that training alone does because it is not only the individual who is impacted upon but the organisation and the wider environment within which the organisation works.

The term human resources refer to the knowledge, skill, creative abilities, talents, aptitude, values and beliefs of an organisation's workforce. Effective performance of an organisation depends not just on the availability of resources, but its quality and competence as required by the organisation from time to time. The efficiency of production process and various areas of management depend to a greater extent on the level of employee development.

1. Changes in Economic Policies

Almost all the governments across the globe have changed their economic policies from communistic/socialistic pattern to capitalistic pattern. Even the government of India liberalized its economic policies in 1991. Liberalization, privatisation and globalisation posed threat to the weak firms and created opportunities to the large firms. These firms started developing their human resources in order to exploit the opportunities.

2. Changing job requirements

Organisational dynamism brings changes in organisational design and job design. The changes in job design bring changes in job description and job specifications. These changes demand for employee development programmes.

3. Employee development for multi skilled employees

The changing trends in industrialization, structuring jobs and organisations demand the employee to take up multiple activities. The customer centered approach led to flexible organisations and flexible work. All these changes demand the employees with multiple skills. Employee developmental activities provide the opportunity to the employee to acquire and develop multiple skills.

4. Organisational viability and transformation process

Organisational viability is continuously influenced by the environmental threats. If the organisation does not adapt itself to the changing environmental factors, it will lose its market share. If the organisation desires to adopt these changes then it has to develop employees through developmental programme.

5. Technological advances

Organisation in order to survive and develop should adopt the latest technology. Adaptation of the latest technology will not be complete until they developed their employees.

7. Some stages to finding success in employee development

There is no one way to finding success in employee development. The continually changing nature of the business environment means that unique demands are constantly being placed on people because they must acquire new skills and resources in order to cope with those demands. Therefore employee development plays a very important role.

1. Full participation

All employees need to participate fully in the identification of their own developmental employee developments.

2. Individual responsibility

There has been a growth in individual's taking responsibility for planning their own continuous development, that is, work based and longer term career based training and development.

3. Reward system

The recognition and reward system is important when individuals take responsibility for their own continuous development. Monetary or non monetary rewards must be provided to employees those who will actively participate in employee developmental programmes.

4. Flexible workforce

A more flexible workforce comes about with more breadth and depth in individual development.

5. Record Keeping

With the increased use of electronic data system, it is now easier to store records of achievement for all employees. These systems keep track of the skills and knowledge accrued Employee development by employees.

6. Diverse workforce

There has been an increase in opportunity for utilizing flexible temporary labour, for example outsourcing, job sharing, part time working and sub-contracting. Such practices allow organizations to maintain a highly skilled and specialized workforce with the competitive strengths required to meet the employee developments of the stakeholders. A diverse and decentralized workforce is essential.

Performance of the employees will depends upon the employee development program of the organization

SL No	Statements	Gender	SA	A	N	DA	SD	X ²	Accept/Reject
1	Employees are find it necessary to improve their skill and achieve objective.	M	8	11	6	0	0	.76	Accept
		F	11	13	1	0	0		
2	Organization taking major part to fulfill the requirement of the employees.	M	3	6	2	8	6	6.02	Accept
		F	4	3	9	4	5		
3	Health, Safety and Welfare facilities are one of the important concepts to improve the performance.	M	9	13	3	0	0	.32	Accept
		F	11	13	1	0	0		
4	Coaching, Counseling and mentoring will help to meet the requirement of the employees.	M	7	14	2	1	1	.09	Accept
		F	8	11	3	2	1		

5	Reward management will work as a motive to improve the performance.	M	11	14	0	0	0	.08	Accept
		F	10	13	2	0	0		
6	Create good atmosphere to work better in the organization.	M	9	12	4	0	0	1.60	Accept
		F	13	12	0	0	0		
7	It helps to improve their career and to reach high in the organization.	M	10	13	2	0	0	.08	Accept
		F	9	14	2	0	0		

Source: Primary Data

Note: Degrees of Freedom: 4. Value = 9.488 at 5% of level of significance.

From the above result it clear that all the statements are falls under acceptance region in the chi square test. This will make us that employee development programmes will helps to improve the performance of the employee.

Findings

1. Employees feel that skill development program will helps them to adjust with a changing situation.
2. Employee development programmes are essential in organization to achieve its objective.
3. It helps to improve the performance of the employees over a period of time.
4. It makes the employees to take higher level of job without any fear in the mind..
5. It builds good work environment in the work place to achieve the results.

Suggestions

1. Organization has to understand the requirement of the employees before designing the employee development plans.
2. Active participation of employees is required in all employee development programmes.
3. Develop a good reward management system to improve the performance of the employees
4. Take care of the family members of the employees who are working in the organization.

8. Conclusion

Employees are the real asset for the organization to achieve its vision and to be a supporting hand in every successful project executed by the company. Achievement of the organization is directly related to the effort and dedication of the employees who are really working for that industry. In the present scenario to make employee competent to this changing world we have to update our skill and knowledge as per the demand of the industry. If company invests on the employee develop project it will enjoy the fruits of success for a long period of time. It will strengthen our capability to compete in the global world with its developed employee force.

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